

The Spectrophotometric and Ion-Selective Electrode Determinations of MgSO_4 Association at High Ionic Strengths

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The stoichiometric stability constants for MgSO_4 association in aqueous solution have been determined spectrophotometrically and potentiometrically in the ionic strength range of 0.3 to 1.0M, and 0.10 to 0.82M, respectively. Terpyridine is used as a metal ion indicator to monitor the free magnesium ion concentrations and divalent cation-selective electrode is employed to measure the free magnesium ion activities in pure MgSO_4 solutions. The results obtained at 25° by the two methods show that they are in good agreement.

MOST of the MgSO_4 stability constants were determined at low concentrations and extrapolated to zero ionic strength by making use of the Debye-Hückel theory. We now wish to report the concentration quotient stability constants determined at ionic strength varying from 0.10 to 1M. First of all, the MgSO_4 association reaction is the major 1 : 1 divalent ionic reaction in seawater which has an ionic strength around 0.7 M^1 . Secondly, the use of ionic-selective electrodes to study thermodynamics of ion pair formation processes is still at its infancy and some controversial questions about this technique have been raised by some investigators².

Here the MgSO_4 association was studied by the ion-selective electrodes as well as the spectrophotometric method. The agreement between their results serves the purpose of confirming to some degree the reliability of both techniques. The spectrophotometric method of using a metal ion indicator to determine the MgSO_4 association possesses several interesting features. It can be extended to other systems such as the reactions under high pressures (i.e., the ionic reactions beneath the surface of the sea) where the ion-selective electrode method fails, or the ion-molecule reactions where the conductance measurements can no longer be applied.

For the purpose of determining the association constant at various ionic strengths, different concentrations were prepared by dilution of the stock solutions immediately before running the experiments. Normally we used 200 ml solution for each measurement and constant stirring was taking place while doing the experiment. The potential reading of the solution was recorded with time until a constant mv reading is reached. This usually takes 6-10 minutes. This period of time was also necessary but sufficient

to bring about the temperature of the solution in the cell to equilibrium at 25°. The calibration curve was done side by side as the experiment was in progress. In other words, a measurement of standard reference MgCl_2 , and test solution, MgSO_4 , immediately following each other. These two solutions were made to have as close value of mv as possible to assure close values of activity for the free Mg^{+2} ion. The experimental Nernst slope for the calibration curve was always ~29.6 mv in good agreement with the theoretical value at 25°. The pH values of the measured solutions were determined right before running the experiment. It was found around 8. Therefore, no adjustment was needed since, according to the Orion Manual, this is the right pH values for the present potential measurements. For each individual concentration, the measurement was repeated four or five times. Each time freshly prepared solution was used. This was necessary for establishing a good mean value for the MgSO_4 association constant at a certain ionic strength. The variation of ionic strength was accomplished by varying the MgSO_4 concentration. To fix the ionic strength by adding some inert electrolyte was avoided due to the complications which might have arisen such as the potentiometric response to the inert cation and its electrostatic interactions with SO_4^- ions. In the present study, the pure MgSO_4 electrolyte was used to prepare the solution. Therefore the activity of Mg^{+2} ion in MgSO_4 solution can be measured using MgCl_2 as a standard reference in conjunction with the Nernst equation. To convert the activities to concentrations, activity coefficients (γ) are needed. Various sets of γ values have appeared in the literature. In our calculation, the γ values listed in the Orion Manual⁶ were used. Practically, it does not make too much difference which values of activity coefficients are used, as long as the same set of values has been used to obtain both the calibration

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curve and the Mg^{+2} ion concentration in $MgSO_4$ solutions. The relative errors in activity coefficients are thus greatly minimized.

Experimental

A. The Spectrophotometric Method :

Materials and Preparations :

Reagent grade $MgCl_2$ (Merck), $MgSO_4$ (Fisher Scientific) were used and the concentrations were standardized by EDTA titrations. Tetramethylammonium chloride (TMA) purchased from Eastman was recrystallized from a hot methanol-acetone mixture⁸. Terpyridine obtained from Pfaltz and Bauer was standardized spectrophotometrically at 290 nm ($\epsilon = 1.6 \times 10^4$).⁴ Stock solutions were prepared for the above reagents and were subsequently diluted to desired concentrations with deionized distilled water.

Measurements :

The pH of the solution adjusted around 8 right before the absorbance measurement was made on a Zeiss spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm cells. The spectrophotometric measurements were made at 329 nm near one of the peaks for the magnesium-terpyridine complex and at 290 nm near the peak for the free terpyridine base, respectively. The electronic absorption spectra for the complex and free terpyridine are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Electronic Absorption Spectra for the Free Terpyridine Base and Its Mono-Magnesium Complex at 25°C.

..... $0.98 \times 10^{-4} M$ Terpyridine
 ——— $0.98 \times 10^{-4} M$ Terpyridine and $0.3 M$ $MgCl_2$.

B. The Ion-Selective Electrode Method :

Preparations and Measurements :

The potential measurements were made with an Orion model 92-32 divalent cation electrode, an Orion model 90-01 single junction reference electrode, and an Orion model 801 pH-mv meter.

The temperature of the solutions was maintained at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in a constant temperature bath. The cell was described elsewhere⁵. All solutions were prepared as described previously.

Results and Discussion

A. The Spectrophotometric Method :

The selection of terpyridine as a metal ion indicator to study $MgSO_4$ association was based on the following considerations. (A) It possesses high extinction coefficients both as a free ligand and a coordinated one at two well separated wavelengths. (B) It has sufficient solubility and remains stable in aqueous solution. (C) It acts as a neutral ligand at pH higher than 7, therefore its reaction with Mg^{+2} ions is expected to be ionic strength insensitive. (D) As a weak base ($pK_1 = 4.7$, $pK_2 = 3.3$), it eliminates the complications caused by the participation of protonated ligand in the reaction.

Magnesium-Terpyridine Interactions :

The stability constant, K_1 , for the formation of 1 : 1 magnesium-terpyridine complex, MgI^{+2} , from the free ligand, I, and the free magnesium ion may be expressed as

In all experiments described in this paper the concentration of magnesium was at least 500 fold higher than that of the ligand, so that the known total magnesium concentration can be assumed for the free magnesium ion concentration. Then we have

$$A = \epsilon_{MgI} [MgI^{+2}] + \epsilon_I [I] \quad \dots (A-2)$$

$$\Sigma I = [MgI^{+2}] + [I] \quad \dots (A-3)$$

$$K_1 = \frac{[MgI^{+2}]}{[Mg^{+2}][I]} \quad \dots (A-4)$$

where ϵ_{MgI} and ϵ_I are the extinction coefficients for the metal complex and the free ligand at a certain wavelength, respectively. A is the absorbance measured at that wavelength. ΣI represents the known total ligand concentration. Both A and ϵ_I can be determined experimentally.

Two of the four unknowns (ϵ_{MgI} , K_1 , $[MgI^{+2}]$ and $[I]$) in the above three equations A-2 through A-4 may be eliminated to obtain a simplified equation with two remaining unknowns.

$$\frac{\Sigma I \times [Mg^{+2}]}{A - \epsilon_I \times \Sigma I} = \frac{1}{K_1 (\epsilon_{MgI} - \epsilon_I)} + \frac{[Mg^{+2}]}{(\epsilon_{MgI} - \epsilon_I)} \quad (A-5)$$

A plot of equation A-5 gives slope and intercept which lead to the values for ϵ_{MgI} and K_1 respectively.

TABLE A-1—THE ABSORBANCE MEASUREMENTS AND CALCULATED VALUES FOR 1 : 1 MAGNESIUM TERPYRIDINE COMPLEX AT 25°C

Sl. No.	MgCl ₂ (M)	Terpy (M×10 ⁴)	N(CH ₃) ₄ Cl(M) ^a	A _(329 nm)	A _(290 nm)	$\frac{\sum I[Mg^{+2}]}{[A - \epsilon_I \sum I]_{329 \text{ nm}}} \times 10^5$ ^b	$\frac{\sum I[Mg^{+2}]}{[A - \epsilon_I \sum I]_{290 \text{ nm}}} \times 10^5$ ^b
1.	1.00	1.0		1.762	0.420	5.737	-8.475
2.	0.50	1.0		1.568	0.562	3.226	-4.817
3.	0.40	1.0		1.453	0.627	2.788	-4.111
4.	0.30	1.0		1.333	0.725	2.281	-3.429
5.	0.30	0.5		0.683	0.362	2.226	-3.425
6.	0.25	1.0		1.214	0.775	2.091	-3.030
7.	0.20	1.0		1.105	0.865	1.840	-2.719
8.	0.20	0.5		0.565	0.432	1.799	-2.717
9.	0.15	1.0		0.949	0.968	1.612	-2.373
10.	0.10	2.0		1.548	2.115	1.323	-1.843
11.	0.10	1.0		0.759	1.093	1.350	-1.972
12.	0.20	1.0	0.3	1.067	0.865	1.925	-2.721
13.	0.10	1.0	0.3	0.748	1.104	1.389	-2.016
14.	0.20	1.0	0.3	1.114	0.840	1.842	-2.740
15.	0.15	1.0	0.3	0.968	0.979	1.596	-2.415
16.	0.25	1.0	0.3	1.235	0.784	2.071	-3.064
17.	0.30	1.0	0.3	1.304	0.715	2.351	-3.390
18.	0.40	1.0	0.3	1.498	0.628	2.721	-4.115
19.	0.50	1.0	0.3	1.557	0.556	3.270	-4.789
20.	1.00	1.0	0.3	1.762	0.422	5.767	-8.489

^aTMA (1.5M) has an absorbance of 0.016 at 329 nm and 0.038 at 290 nm, respectively.

^b ϵ_I is 183 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 329 nm in the absence of TMA ; it is 280 at 329 nm and 1.6×10⁴ M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 290 nm in the presence of TMA.

Fig. 2. Plots of Equation A-5 based on the points shown in Table A-1 in the absence of TMA at 25°C.

The experimental results are collected in Table A-1. The plots based on equation A-5 and the data in Table A-1 are shown in Figure 2. The values for K_I and ϵ_{MgI} determined at 329 nm are 5.835 M⁻¹ and 2.070×10⁴ M⁻¹ cm⁻¹; and at 290 nm; they are 5.881 M⁻¹ and 2.191×10⁴ M⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. As shown, the K_I values obtained independently with the exclusion of the points having TMA added at these two wavelengths are in

excellent agreement with an average value of 5.858±0.023M⁻¹.

By utilizing equation A-2 twice and the independently determined ϵ_{MgI} and ϵ_I values at 329 and 290 nm, respectively, the concentrations for [MgI⁺²] and [I] along with K_I may be regenerated. As compared to the known total ligand concentration, the calculated sum, [MgI⁺²]+[I] has less than

TABLE A-2—EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR THE $MgSO_4$ ASSOCIATION CONSTANT DETERMINATIONS USING TERPYRIDINE AS A METAL ION INDICATOR AT 25°C. I_s REPRESENTS IONIC STRENGTH

Sl. No.	$MgCl_2$ (M)	$MgSO_4$ (M)	$N(CH_3)_4Cl$ (M)	Terpy (M × 10 ⁴)	A _(329 nm)	A _(290 nm)	MgI ^a (M × 10 ⁴)	I ^a (M × 10 ⁴)	[MgI+I] (M × 10 ⁴)	Mg ²⁺ (M)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (M)	K	I _r
1.		0.60		1.0	1.232	0.776	0.5916	0.4040	0.9956	0.2500	0.2500	5.6	1.00
2.		0.55		1.0	1.207	0.805	0.5793	0.4238	1.0031	0.2333	0.2333	5.8	0.93
3.		0.60		1.0	1.153	0.835	0.5531	0.4462	0.9993	0.2116	0.2116	6.4	0.85
4.		0.45		1.0	1.115	0.865	0.5345	0.4675	1.0020	0.1952	0.1952	6.7	0.78
5.		0.40		1.0	1.054	0.911	0.5048	0.5003	1.0051	0.1722	0.1722	7.7	0.69
6.		0.35		1.0	1.007	0.961	0.4817	0.5347	1.0164	0.1538	0.1538	8.3	0.62
7.		0.35		1.5	1.473	1.433	0.7045	0.7992	1.5037	0.1505	0.1505	8.8	0.60
8.		0.30		1.0	0.915	0.986	0.4374	0.5564	0.9938	0.1342	0.1342	9.2	0.54
9.		0.25		1.0	0.844	1.045	0.4024	0.5980	1.0004	0.1149	0.1149	10.2	0.46
10.		0.20		1.0	0.757	1.108	0.3600	0.6342	1.0032	0.0955	0.0955	11.5	0.38
11.	0.20	0.20		1.0	1.280	0.740	0.6150	0.3783	0.9933	0.2775	0.0775	5.7	0.91
12.	0.22	0.18		1.0	1.299	0.727	0.6243	0.3689	0.9932	0.2889	0.0689	5.6	0.94
13.	0.25	0.15		1.0	1.343	0.713	0.6456	0.3573	1.0029	0.3084	0.0584	5.1	0.98
14.	0.20	0.15		1.0	1.264	0.773	0.6071	0.4000	1.0071	0.2591	0.0591	5.9	0.84
15.	0.15	0.20		1.0	1.196	0.811	0.5740	0.4283	1.0023	0.2288	0.0788	6.7	0.77
16.	0.15	0.15		1.0	1.146	0.841	0.5496	0.4504	1.0000	0.2083	0.0583	7.6	0.68
17.	0.15	0.15		1.5	1.671	1.268	0.8012	0.6828	1.4840	0.2003	0.0503	9.9	0.65
18.	0.18	0.12		1.0	1.187	0.817	0.5696	0.4327	1.0023	0.2247	0.0447	7.5	0.72
19.	0.13	0.20		1.0	1.150	0.825	0.5517	0.4401	0.9918	0.2140	0.0840	6.5	0.73
20.	0.08	0.09		1.0	0.847	1.038	0.4039	0.5935	0.9974	0.1162	0.0362	12.8	0.38
21.	0.10	0.06		1.0	0.875	1.009	0.4176	0.5735	0.9911	0.1243	0.0243	11.8	0.40
22.	0.12	0.08		1.0	0.973	0.947	0.4654	0.5282	0.9936	0.1504	0.0304	10.3	0.48
23.	0.12	0.06		1.0	0.932	0.956	0.4455	0.5365	0.9820	0.1418	0.0218	12.4	0.45
24.	0.12	0.121		1.0	1.026	0.902	0.4913	0.4965	0.9878	0.1689	0.0489	8.7	0.56
25.		0.30	0.20	1.0	0.978	0.968	0.4619	0.5486	1.0105	0.1481	0.1481	6.9	0.79
26.		0.20	0.40	1.0	0.825	1.067	0.3900	0.6166	1.0066	0.1113	0.1113	7.2	0.85
27.	0.15	0.10	0.20	1.0	1.086	0.862	0.5171	0.4721	0.9892	0.1927	0.0427	7.0	0.82
28.		0.30	0.10	1.0	0.942	0.973	0.4470	0.5505	0.9975	0.1429	0.1429	7.7	0.67
29.	0.10	0.10	0.12	1.0	0.946	0.960	0.4490	0.5421	0.9911	0.1457	0.0457	8.2	0.60
30.	0.08	0.09	0.11	1.0	0.894	1.037	0.4234	0.5985	1.0169	0.1255	0.0455	7.8	0.53
31.		0.20	0.21	1.0	0.800	1.077	0.3779	0.6244	1.0023	0.1065	0.1065	8.2	0.64
32.		0.20	0.20	1.5	1.168	1.608	0.5514	0.9339	1.4853	0.1039	0.1039	8.9	0.62
33.	0.10	0.10	0.20	1.0	0.964	0.981	0.4575	0.5542	1.0117	0.1452	0.0452	8.8	0.68
34.	0.10	0.08	0.24	1.0	0.924	0.989	0.4382	0.5616	0.9898	0.1378	0.0373	8.3	0.69
35.	0.08	0.08	0.30	1.0	0.857	1.039	0.4056	0.5971	1.0027	0.1195	0.0395	8.6	0.70
36.		0.20	0.26	1.0	0.817	1.072	0.3861	0.6202	1.0063	0.1095	0.1095	7.5	0.70
37.	0.03	0.15	0.35	1.0	0.821	1.064	0.3881	0.6150	1.0031	0.1110	0.0810	7.7	0.76
38.	0.07	0.06	0.25	1.0	0.764	1.090	0.3604	0.6348	0.9952	0.0999	0.0299	10.1	0.58
39.		0.15	0.34	1.0	0.707	1.145	0.3323	0.6727	1.0053	0.0870	0.0870	8.3	0.69
40.	0.10	0.10	0.20	1.5	1.427	1.455	0.6772	0.8221	1.4993	0.1449	0.0449	8.5	0.68
41.	0.08	0.04	0.36	1.0	0.766	1.092	0.3614	0.6359	0.9973	0.1000	0.0200	10.0	0.68
42.	0.07	0.06	0.36	1.0	0.784	1.100	0.3700	0.6398	1.0098	0.1017	0.0317	8.9	0.70

^a The value of $232 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ for ϵ_I at 329 nm averaged from 183 and 230 $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ was used for calculation in the $MgCl_2$ - $MgSO_4$ -Terpyridine-TMA mixtures where [TMA] varies from 0.1 to 0.36 M.

in the mixture of $MgCl_2$ and terpyridine free of the TMA salt was used to calculate the results obtained in the $MgCl_2$ - $MgSO_4$ -terpyridine solutions. As shown in Table A-2, the calculated sums for $[MgI^{+2}] + [I]$ are in excellent agreement with the known total ligand concentrations. Similarly, the extinction coefficients and K_I value obtained including the points having 0.3 M TMA added were used for the $MgCl_2$ - $MgSO_4$ -terpyridine solution in the presence of 0.11 to 0.36 M TMA salt. Because of some weak interference of TMA with terpyridine and the fact that the TMA concentrations in the $MgSO_4$ solution are not constant, the association constants evaluated are included in Table A-2 for reference only.

A plot of K_{MgSO_4} versus ionic strength in the absence of TMA based on Table A-2 is presented in

Figure 3. The best least squares parabola obtained for the curve in Figure 3 is shown as

$$K_{MgSO_4} = 20.901 - 26.802(I_s) + 11.164(I_s)^2 \dots (A-10)$$

It should be emphasized that equation A-10 is derived on the basis of K_{MgSO_4} values obtained in the experimental ionic strength range from 0.38 to 1.00 M. Therefore, K_{MgSO_4} value at infinite dilution could not be accurately approximated from this equation.

B. The Ion-Selective Electrode Method :

The Nernst equation describes the potential response (E) to the ionic activity in solutions as

$$E = E_o + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln a \quad (B-1)$$

Fig. 3. A Plot of K_{MgSO_4} versus Ionic Strength at 25°C based on Table A-2 absence of TMA. The curve represents the Best Fit.

where E_0 designates the reference electrode potential, R , T , n and F as molar gas constant, absolute temperature, charge on the ion and Faraday constant, respectively. a is the chemical activity of the ion being measured.

Because of their response to ion activity, these electrodes are well suited for ionic association constant determination. In this respect, the electrodes should first be calibrated with standard reference solutions of known activity. Then the activities of test solution can be determined. This technique has been employed to determine the magnesium and calcium ionic concentrations in a seawater model⁷. However, special attention must be given to the experimental procedure in general and in achieving the calibration curve in particular^{6,8}.

In a pure aqueous $MgSO_4$ solution, the total magnesium concentration, $[Mg]_T$, consists of two parts, free Mg^{+2} and bound ions $MgSO_{4T}$ as shown in the following reaction,

The association constant K_{MgSO_4} is defined in eq. A-7.

To calculate K_{MgSO_4} , the following magnesium concentrations must be known. The total Mg concentration was known from volumetric titration, the free can be determined potentiometrically. The

difference in potentiometric measurements between standard, $MgCl_2$ and test solution, $MgSO_4$ can be corrected for using the Nernst slope to obtain the ion activity for the latter. If we assume a value of free Mg^{+2} ion concentration in $MgSO_4$, the ionic strength of the solution can be obtained as a first guess because of the relationship of $I_s = 4[Mg^{+2}]$. Based on this ionic strength, a corresponding activity coefficient is obtained which in turn is used to calculate the magnesium ion concentration from the measured activity. The procedure is iterated several times until the error between the assumed and the calculated magnesium ion concentrations is minimum.

The disadvantage of the present way of calculation to obtain K_{MgSO_4} for both spectrophotometric and potentiometric method is that the measurement errors in Mg^{+2} are multiplied and totally reflected in K_{MgSO_4} value. This is because a smaller than true of Mg^{+2} ion concentration gives rise to a smaller than true SO_4^{-2} and larger than true $MgSO_{4T}$ concentrations, and vice versa. The results of potential measurements are tabulated in Tables B-1 and B-2. Table B-1 shows a detailed data set for both the standard and test solutions at ten ionic strength. Table B-2 summarizes all the measurements along with the K_{MgSO_4} values calculated from eq. A-10.

The measurement values determined by the two techniques as shown in Figure 4, show that they are in good agreement between 0.3 and 0.6 M ionic strength and in fair agreement between 0.6 and

TABLE B-1—EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF A SINGLE MEASUREMENT AT 25°C FOR MgSO₄ AND MgCl₂ SOLUTIONS

MgSO ₄ M	MgCl ₂ M	mv Mg ²⁺	^a Mg ²⁺ M × 10 ³	γ Mg ²⁺	Mg ²⁺ M × 10 ³	I _s M	K M ⁻¹
0.049 _s		21.2	11.2 _o	0.40 ₇	27.5 _s	0.110	29.1
	0.025 _s	21.2	11.2 _o	0.44 ₂	25.3 _s	0.076	
0.099 _o		26.4	17.2 _o	0.34 _o	49.3 _o	0.197	20.5
	0.048 ₇	27.3	18.5 _o	0.38 _o	48.8 ₇	0.146	
0.148 _s		67.5*	23.0 _o	0.30 _o	74.4 _o	0.297	13.4
	0.060 ₄	66.7	21.7 _o	0.35 _s	60.4 _s	0.181	
0.148 _s		32.1	22.0 _o	0.31 _o	69.7 _o	0.279	16.2
	0.060 ₄	32.0	21.8 _o	0.36 _o	60.4 _s	0.181	
0.198 _o		68.9*	26.2 _o	0.29 _o	89.6 _s	0.358	13.5
	0.075 _o	68.2	25.2 _o	0.33 _s	75.0 _o	0.225	
0.297 _o		71.9*	34.8 _o	0.26 ₇	130.3 _o	0.520	9.8
	0.119 _s	72.5	35.0 _o	0.29 _o	119.9 _o	0.359	
0.396 _o		67.7*	41.0 _o	0.25 _o	158.3 _o	0.633	9.5
	0.159 _s	69.2	46.0 _o	0.28 _o	159.9 _o	0.479	
0.495 _o		75.9*	46.6 _o	0.25 _o	185.3 _o	0.741	9.0
	0.158 _o	75.5	42.4 _o	0.26 _o	158.0 _o	0.574	
0.590 _o		77.8*	50.0 _o	0.25 _o	200.0 _o	0.800	9.8
	0.169 ₄	76.6	45.4 _s	0.26 _o	169.6 _o	0.588	

* In this case the solution used for the reference electrode was not the standard Orion solution, but was 3.3M KCl saturated with AgNO₃ as recommended in the Orion Manual when higher ionic strength solutions are measured.

TABLE B-2—A SUMMARY OF K_{MgSO₄} AT 25°C

I _s , M ^{a, b}	K, M ^{-1a}	K _{MgSO₄} , M ^{-1c}
0.109	30.0 ± 3.0	—
0.193	22.0 ± 2.0	—
0.285	15.4 ± 1.5	—
0.300	—	(13.9) ^d
0.361	13.2 ± 2.0	(12.7) ^d
0.400	—	12.0
0.500	—	10.3
0.512	11.7 ± 1.8	10.1
0.600	—	8.8
0.632	9.6 ± 0.4	8.4
0.700	—	7.6
0.733	9.3 ± 0.5	7.3
0.800	—	6.6
0.816	9.4 ± 0.5	6.5
0.900	—	5.8
1.000	—	5.3

a = Electrode determinations.
 b = Mean values.
 c = Calculated values based on eq. A-10 at the corresponding ionic strength. The errors are generally ± 10% or less.
 d = Extrapolated value.

0.8 M within the experimental errors. Part of the deviation at ionic strength higher than 0.6 M may reflect the errors involved in the liquid junction potentials inherent in the potentiometric measurements at higher ionic strength⁹. A closely matched free magnesium activity between the standards, MgCl₂, and the test solutions, MgSO₄, will result in a higher ionic strength for the latter as shown in Table B-1. This part of errors may be sufficiently eliminated if magnesium *m*-benzene-disulfonate are used as standards. The value of 10.2 ± 0.5 M⁻¹ at 0.7 M reported by Ptykiewicz *et al*^{7c} shows 10-20% higher than the values of this work. The thermodynamic stability constants may be obtained provided appropriate activity coefficients are available.

Fig. 4. Plots of [Mg²⁺]/[Mg]_T and [MgSO₄]_T/[Mg]_T versus Ionic Strength at 25°C. [Mg²⁺]/[Mg]_T: ▼, Electrode measurement and ▽, Spectrophotometric measurement. [MgSO₄]_T/[Mg]_T: ●, Electrode measurement and ○, Spectrophotometric measurement. The Electrode data used for calculations are those shown in the first column of Table B-2.

The activity coefficients at 0.7 M using the data collected by Harned and Owen are 0.36 for γ_{Mg²⁺} and 0.12 for γ_{SO₄²⁻}, respectively¹⁰. Using these values for extrapolation, the thermodynamic association constant averaged from the spectrophotometric and potentiometric measurements is 196 ± 19 M⁻¹. This value falls within the range of literature values which are between 129 and 240 M⁻¹¹². The activity coefficients found for MgSO₄ in seawater are lower than those calculated from ionic strength principle for pure electrolytes¹¹. Therefore, they are not applicable in the present case.

The mean activity coefficient at 0.109 M ionic strength may be calculated from the Davies equation,

$$\log \gamma_i = -0.5 z_i^2 \left[\frac{\sqrt{I_s}}{1 + \sqrt{I_s}} - 0.3I_s \right] \dots \quad (B-2)$$

and it is found to be 0.371. This K_{MgSO₄} at infinitive dilution becomes 218 ± 22 M⁻¹. On the basis of equation (B-2), a linear relationship between log K_{MgSO₄} versus √I_s is expected at ionic strength to be lower than 0.01 M. The results of these studies will be incorporated with those of CaSO₄ association reactions and presented elsewhere⁸.

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